

THE DETERMINATION OF 2-COLOR ZERO-SUM GENERALIZED SCHUR NUMBERS

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Abstract

Consider the equation $\mathcal{E} : x_1 + \cdots + x_{k-1} = x_k$ and let k and r be positive integers such that $r \mid k$. The number $S_{3,2}(k; r)$ is defined to be the least positive integer t such that for any 2-coloring $\chi : [1, t] \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ there exists a solution $(\hat{x}_1, \hat{x}_2, \dots, \hat{x}_k)$ to equation \mathcal{E} satisfying $\sum_{i=1}^k \chi(\hat{x}_i) \equiv 0 \pmod{r}$. In a recent paper, the first author posed the question of determining the exact value of $S_{3,2}(k; 4)$. In this article, we solve this problem and show, more generally, that $S_{3,2}(k; r) = kr - 2r + 1$ for all positive integers k and r with $r \mid k$ and $k \geq 2r$.

1. Introduction

For $r \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, there exists a least positive integer $S(r)$, called a *Schur number*, such that within every r -coloring of $[1, S(r)]$ there is a monochromatic solution to the linear equation $x_1 + x_2 = x_3$.

In 1933, Rado [10] generalized the work of Schur to arbitrary systems of linear equations. For any integer $k \geq 2$ and $r \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, there exists a least positive integer $S(k; r)$, called a *generalized Schur number*, such that every r -coloring of $[1, S(k; r)]$ admits a monochromatic solution to the equation $\mathcal{E} : x_1 + \cdots + x_{k-1} = x_k$. Indeed, Rado's result proves, in particular, that the number $S(k; r)$ exists (is finite). In [2], Beutelspacher and Brestovansky proved the exact value $S(k; 2) = k^2 - k - 1$.

Before we analogize the above number, we need the following definition.

Definition 1. Let $r \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. We say that a set of integers $\{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n\}$ is r -zero-sum if $\sum_{i=1}^n a_i \equiv 0 \pmod{r}$.

The Erdős-Ginzburg-Ziv Theorem [5] is one of the cornerstones of zero-sum theory (see, for instance, [1] and [9]). It states that any sequence of $2n - 1$ integers must contain an n -zero-sum subsequence of n integers. In recent times, zero-sum theory has made remarkable progress (see, for instance, [3], [4], [6], [7], [8]).

In [11], the first author replaced the “monochromatic property” of the generalized Schur number by the “zero-sum property” and introduced the following new number which is called a *zero-sum generalized Schur number*.

Notation. Throughout the article, we represent the equation $x_1 + \dots + x_{k-1} = x_k$ by \mathcal{E} .

Definition 2. Let k and r be positive integers such that $r \mid k$. We define $S_3(k; r)$ to be the least positive integer t such that for any r -coloring $\chi : [1, t] \rightarrow \{0, \dots, r - 1\}$ there exists a solution $(\hat{x}_1, \hat{x}_2, \dots, \hat{x}_k)$ to equation \mathcal{E} satisfying $\sum_{i=1}^k \chi(\hat{x}_i) \equiv 0 \pmod{r}$.

We only make the above definition (and Definition 3, below) for $r \mid k$ since the coloring of \mathbb{Z}^+ by coloring every integer with color 1 shows that we cannot guarantee an r -zero-sum solution if $r \nmid k$.

Since $r \mid k$, note that if $(\hat{x}_1, \hat{x}_2, \dots, \hat{x}_k)$ is a monochromatic solution to equation \mathcal{E} , then clearly it is an r -zero-sum solution. Hence, we get, $S_3(k; r) \leq S(k; r)$ and therefore, $S_3(k; r)$ is finite.

In [11], the first author calculated lower bounds of this number for some r . In particular, he proved the following result.

Theorem 1. [11] *Let k and r be positive integers such that $r \mid k$. Then,*

$$S_3(k; r) \geq \begin{cases} 3k - 3 & \text{when } r = 3; \\ 4k - 5 & \text{when } r = 4; \\ 2(k^2 - k - 1) & \text{when } r = k \text{ is odd.} \end{cases}$$

In the same article, he introduced another number meant only for 2-colorings, but keeping the r -zero-sum notion.

Definition 3. Let k and r be positive integers such that $r \mid k$. We denote by $S_{3,2}(k; r)$ the least positive integer such that every 2-coloring of $\chi : [1, S_{3,2}(k; r)] \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ admits a solution $(\hat{x}_1, \hat{x}_2, \dots, \hat{x}_k)$ to equation \mathcal{E} satisfying $\sum_{i=1}^k \chi(\hat{x}_i) \equiv 0 \pmod{r}$.

Since any 2-coloring of $[1, S_3(k; r)]$ is also an r -coloring (for $r \geq 2$), we see that $S_{3,2}(k; r) \leq S_3(k; r)$ and hence $S_{3,2}(k; r)$ is finite. Furthermore, in the case when $k = r$ we recover the generalized Schur number $S(k; 2)$.

In [11], the first author proved the following theorem related to these 2-color zero-sum generalized Schur numbers.

Theorem 2. [11] *Let k and r be two positive integers such that $r \mid k$. Then*

$$S_{3,2}(k; r) = \begin{cases} 2k - 3; & \text{if } r = 2 \\ 3k - 5; & \text{if } r = 3 \text{ and } k \neq 3 \\ k^2 - k - 1; & \text{if } r = k. \end{cases}$$

One notes that the exact values of $S_{3,2}(k; r)$ for $r = 2, 3$ and $S_{3,2}(r, r)$ do not show any obvious generalization to $S_{3,2}(k; r)$ for any k which is a multiple of r . However, the computations given in [11] when $r = 4$ and $k = 4, 8, 12$, and when $r = 5$ and $k = 5, 10, 15$, were enough for us to conjecture a general formula, which turns out to hold. To this end, by Theorem 3 below, we answer a question posed by the first author in [11] and, more generally, determine the exact values of $S_{3,2}(k; r)$.

Theorem 3. *Let k and r be positive integers such that $r \mid k$ and $k \geq 2r$. Then, $S_{3,2}(k; r) = rk - 2r + 1$.*

2. Preliminaries

We start by presenting a pair of lemmas useful for proving our upper bounds.

Lemma 1. *Let k and r be positive integers such that $r \mid k$ and $k \geq 2r$. Let $\chi : [1, rk - 2r + 1] \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ be a 2-coloring such that $\chi(1) = \chi(r - 1) = 0$. Then there exists an r -zero-sum solution to equation \mathcal{E} under χ .*

Proof. Consider the solution $(1, 1, \dots, 1, k - 1)$. If $\chi(k - 1) = 0$, then, since $\chi(1) = 0$, we are done. Hence, we shall assume that $\chi(k - 1) = 1$.

Next, we look at the solution

$$\underbrace{(1, \dots, 1)}_{k-r}, \underbrace{(k-1, k-1, k-1)}_{r-1}, rk - 2r + 1.$$

Since $\chi(1) = 0$ and $\chi(k - 1) = 1$, we can assume that $\chi(rk - 2r + 1) = 0$; otherwise, we have exactly r integers of color 1 and so the solution is r -zero-sum.

Since $(1, r, r, \dots, r, rk - 2r + 1)$ is a solution to \mathcal{E} , we can assume that $\chi(r) = 1$. Finally, consider

$$\underbrace{(r-1, \dots, r-1)}_{r-1}, \underbrace{(r, \dots, r)}_{k-r}, rk - 2r + 1.$$

Since $\chi(r - 1) = 0$, $\chi(r) = 1$, $\chi(rk - 2r + 1) = 0$, and $r \mid k$, this solution is r -zero-sum, thereby proving the lemma. \square

Lemma 2. *Let k and r be positive integers such that $r \mid k$ and $k \geq 2r$. Let $\chi : [1, rk - 2r + 1] \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ be a coloring such that $\chi(1) = 0$ and $\chi(r - 1) = 1$. If one of the following holds, then there exists an r -zero-sum solution to equation \mathcal{E} :*

- (a) $\chi(r) = 0$;
- (b) $\chi(k - 2) = 1$;
- (c) $\chi(k - 1) = 0$;
- (d) $\chi(k) = 0$
- (e) $\chi(rk - 2r - 1) = 0$;
- (f) $\chi(rk - 2r + 1) = 1$.

Proof. We will prove each possibility separately; however, the order in which we do so matters so we will not be proving them in the order listed.

(c) Consider $(1, 1, \dots, 1, k - 1)$. If $\chi(k - 1) = 0$ then this solution is r -zero sum.

(d) By considering the solution $(r - 1, \dots, r - 1, (r - 1)(k - 1))$, we can assume that $\chi((r - 1)(k - 1)) = 0$. Using this in

$$\underbrace{(1, \dots, 1)}_{k-r+1}, \underbrace{k, \dots, k}_{r-2}, (r - 1)(k - 1)$$

along with the assumption that $\chi(k) = 0$, we have an r -zero-sum solution.

(f) From part (c), we may assume that $\chi(k - 1) = 1$. Looking at $(r - 1, \dots, r - 1, k - 1, rk - 2r + 1)$, since $\chi(k - 1) = \chi(r - 1) = 1$, and assuming that $\chi(rk - 2r + 1) = 1$, we have an r -zero sum solution.

(a) From part (f), we may assume that $\chi(rk - 2r + 1) = 0$. With this assumption, we see that $(1, r, \dots, r, rk - 2r + 1)$ is r -zero-sum when $\chi(r) = 0$.

(b) From parts (a) and (f), we may assume $\chi(r) = 1$ and $\chi(rk - 2r + 1) = 0$. Under these assumptions, we find that

$$\underbrace{(1, \dots, 1)}_{k-r-1}, r, \underbrace{k - 2, \dots, k - 2}_{r-1}, rk - 2r + 1$$

is an r -zero-sum solution with $\chi(k - 2) = 1$.

(e) By considering

$$\underbrace{(1, \dots, 1)}_{r-1}, \underbrace{r, \dots, r}_{k-2r}, \underbrace{2r - 3, \dots, 2r - 3}_r, rk - 2r - 1$$

and using $r \mid k$, we have an r -zero-sum solution when $\chi(rk - 2r - 1) = 0$. □

3. Proof of the Main Result

In this section we prove that $S_{3,2}(k; r) = rk - 2r + 1$.

Proof. We start with the lower bound. To prove that $S_{3,2}(k; r) > rk - 2r$, we consider the 2-coloring χ of $[1, rk - 2r]$ defined by $\chi(i) = 0$ for $1 \leq i \leq k - 2$ and $\chi(i) = 1$ for $k - 1 \leq i \leq rk - 2r$. Assume, for a contradiction, that χ admits an r -zero-sum solution $(\hat{x}_1, \hat{x}_2, \dots, \hat{x}_k)$ to equation \mathcal{E} . Then $\chi(\hat{x}_i) = 1$ for some $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$; otherwise the solution is monochromatic of color 0, but $\sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \hat{x}_i \geq k - 1$, meaning that \hat{x}_k cannot be of color 0.

Assuming that $(\hat{x}_1, \hat{x}_2, \dots, \hat{x}_k)$ is r -zero-sum and not monochromatic of color 0, we must have $\chi(x_j) = 1$ for at least r of the x_j 's. Since the minimum integer under χ that is of color 1 is $k - 1$, this gives us

$$\sum_{i=1}^{k-1} x_i \geq (r-1)(k-1) + 1(k-r) = rk - 2r + 1 > rk - 2r,$$

which is out of bounds, a contradiction. Hence, χ does not admit an r -zero-sum solution to \mathcal{E} and we conclude that $S_{3,2}(k; r) \geq rk - 2r + 1$.

We now move on to the upper bound. We let $\chi : [1, rk - 2r + 1] \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ be an arbitrary 2-coloring. We may assume that $\chi(1) = 0$ since χ admits an r -zero-sum solution if and only if the induced coloring $\bar{\chi}$ defined by $\bar{\chi}(i) = 1 - \chi(i)$ also does so.

The cases $r = 2, 3$ have been done by Theorem 2. Hence, we may assume that $r \geq 4$. We must handle the case $r = 4$ separately; we start with this case.

We will show that $4k - 7$ serves as an upper bound for $S_3(4; r)$. Consider the following solution to \mathcal{E} :

$$(1, 1, 1, \underbrace{2, \dots, 2}_{k-8}, 3, 3, k, k, 4k - 7).$$

Noting that $r - 1 = 3$ and $rk - 2r + 1 = 4k - 7$, by Lemmas 1 and 2, we may assume $\chi(3) = 1$, $\chi(k) = 1$, and $\chi(4k - 7) = 0$. Since k is a multiple of 4 and $k \geq 8$, we see that $k - 8$ is also a multiple of 4. Hence, the color of 2 does not affect whether or not this solution is 4-zero-sum. Of the integers not equal to 2, we have exactly four of them of color 1. Hence, this solution is 4-zero-sum. This, along with the lower bound above, proves that $S_{3,2}(k; 4) = 4k - 7$.

We now move on to the cases where $r \geq 5$. We proceed by assuming that no r -zero-sum solution occurs under an arbitrary 2-coloring $\chi : [1, rk - 2r + 1] \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$. From Lemmas 1 and 2, we may assume the following table of colors holds:

color 0	color 1
1	$r - 1$
$k - 2$	r
$rk - 2r + 1$	$k - 1$
	k
	$rk - 2r - 1$.

In order for the solution

$$\underbrace{(1, \dots, 1)}_{k-r}, \underbrace{(k-2, \dots, k-2)}_{r-2}, k+r-3, rk-2r+1)$$

not to be r -zero-sum, we deduce that $\chi(k+r-3) = 1$. Using this in the solution

$$\underbrace{(1, \dots, 1)}_{k-r}, \underbrace{(k, \dots, k)}_{r-2}, k+r-3, rk-3)$$

we may assume that $\chi(rk-3) = 0$. In turn, we use this in

$$\underbrace{(2, \dots, 2)}_{k-r-1}, r, r-1, \underbrace{(k, \dots, k)}_{r-2}, rk-3)$$

to deduce that $\chi(2) = 1$. Modifying this last solution slightly, we consider

$$\underbrace{(3, \dots, 3)}_{k-r-1}, r, r, r, \underbrace{(k, \dots, k)}_{r-3}, rk-3)$$

to deduce that $\chi(3) = 1$. Finally, since $r \geq 5$, we can consider

$$\underbrace{(2, \dots, 2)}_{k-2r+6}, \underbrace{(3, \dots, 3)}_{r-5}, \underbrace{(k-1, \dots, k-1)}_{r-2}, rk-2r-1).$$

We see that this solution is monochromatic (of color 1), and, hence, is r -zero-sum. This proves that $S_{3,2}(k; r) \leq rk - 2r + 1$ for $r \geq 5$, which, together with the lower bound at the beginning of the proof, gives us $S_{3,2}(k; r) = rk - 2r + 1$, thereby completing the proof. \square

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